

Multimodal Imaging, Drug Delivery, and On-Board Triggered Degradation in Soft Capsule Rolling Microrobots

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In the rapidly advancing field of medical microrobotics, designing robots capable of addressing various challenges—such as imaging, biodegradation, and multifunctionality—is crucial. Departing from conventional research that often focuses on isolated aspects of microrobot functionality, this study presents an innovative approach to comprehensive microrobot design. Soft capsule microrobots that integrate capabilities such as magnetic navigation, autonomous maneuverability, in situ biodegradation, biosafe imaging, and drug delivery are reported. These microrobots are fabricated within the range of 20–120 μm , with a notable throughput of $\approx 10^2$ – 10^3 microrobots per second. Furthermore, their locomotion performance has been demonstrated to remain stable for a period exceeding 10 h, all while employing real-time optical closed-loop control. The incorporation of ultrasound contrast agents not only amplifies imaging resolution but also ensures imaging contrast stability in a biological environment for over a period of 3 h. Second, the intentional integration of enzyme-loaded nanometric polymersomes establishes a self-contained, biodegradable system, accentuating the microrobots' capacity to degrade without the addition of high enzyme concentrations. This integrated approach lays the groundwork for minimally invasive treatments toward personalized and targeted medicine.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, the field of medical science has undergone a significant shift toward more targeted drug treatment strategies, thanks to an improved understanding of diseases at the cellular and molecular level. This shift has led to the development of medical microrobots for precision medicine, which holds great promise in revolutionizing healthcare.^[1,2] The demand for miniaturized robotics in surgery and minimally invasive medicine has been on the rise, with applications ranging from cancer treatment, blood clot removal, remote diagnosis, to assisted reproduction.^[3–12] Amidst this demand, the integration of multifunctional capabilities within a single microrobot platform emerges as an important advancement in view to their translation to in vivo applications. This work introduces a highly versatile microrobot that combines magnetic actuation, closed-loop control, enhanced and stable medical imaging,

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self-contained biodegradability, and efficient drug delivery, by incorporating these functionalities into one cohesive and customizable steerable soft microcapsule.

To ensure the success of medical microrobots in vivo, it is crucial to develop microrobots that possess compliance like that of biological tissues. This is essential to prevent potential fibrosis events, which have been observed with rigid objects or devices.^[13] Soft microrobots made from hydrogels and elastomers have shown excellent reconfigurability and adaptability, making them highly desirable.^[14,15] Among these materials, hydrogels such as alginate hold particular interest for medical applications due to their resemblance to biological macromolecular entities like the extracellular matrix. Additionally, alginate exhibits very low toxicity. Previous works have introduced millimeter-scale alginate structures as transport and drug-release systems, where magnetic particles are arranged during the extrusion of the hydrogel, for their further magnetic actuation.^[16–19] However, these structures have shown limited functionality and lack of control over dimensions, resulting in low production yield. The controlled emulsion technique has also been employed to fabricate gelatin capsules, primarily with the purpose of safeguarding catalytic micromotors before their release, offering protection against the harsh surrounding environment during transport.^[20] Passive particles, in general, have found extensive use in encapsulating cells or facilitating the growth of organoids for applications in tissue engineering, disease treatment, and on-a-chip drug screening.^[21,22] However, in the present work, these passive carriers or encapsulation strategies are not discussed extensively as they serve different purposes across various applications. In the context of droplet microfluidics for microrobot fabrication, it is noteworthy to mention that only chemical-based microrobots utilizing Pt and hydrogen peroxide reactions have been documented. However, it is crucial to recognize that this approach has inherent limitations when it comes to its applicability in biomedical contexts and functional capabilities. These limitations stem from the materials and propulsion methods suggested in this approach.^[23,24]

This leads us to the vital prerequisites of biocompatibility and biodegradability for medical microrobots.^[25,26] Proper selection of materials and degradation strategies are essential to prevent undesired immunoreactions and facilitate the clearance of the microrobots after performing their intended medical function. It is worth noting that none of the alginate-based microrobots mentioned earlier have demonstrated biodegradability under physiological conditions.

Moreover, real-time tracking through scattering tissues is necessary for operating within living organisms. Significant progress has been made in identifying the most effective methods for tracking microstructures in vivo, including techniques such as MRI, X-rays, nuclear medicine, and ultrasound (US).^[27–29] Specifically, our research group has successfully achieved real-time tracking of single magnetically driven microrobots using US and photoacoustic (PA) imaging, both in vitro and in vivo, by utilizing metal coatings and plasmonic nanoparticles.^[30–34]

In summary, the translation of medical microrobots into in vivo conditions requires meeting several requirements. These microrobots should possess characteristics such as softness, biocompatibility, and biodegradability. Additionally, they need to be traceable under scattering tissues using suitable imaging

techniques and exhibit multifunctionality for disease-specific therapy.^[35,36] Therefore, this study proposes multifunctional biodegradable soft capsule microrobots that address these challenges. The production of these microrobots is automated and standardized using droplet microfluidics, resulting in a production rate of $\approx 10^2$ – 10^3 microrobots s^{-1} . The resulting capsule microrobots operate stably over 10 h under magnetic field actuation, possess two types of contrast agents for both anatomical and functional imaging under scattering tissues, and can release molecules or drugs on demand by in situ degrading the microrobots using stimuli-responsive enzyme-loaded polymersomes. While each technology incorporated into our microrobot has been explored individually in the past, the innovative integration and optimization presented here marks a milestone in the quest for truly versatile and effective microrobotic systems for precision medicine.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Soft Microrobots Production

Multifunctional soft microrobots were fabricated by droplet microfluidics. This procedure allows the integration of several functional components as well as the production of a large number of microrobots using a very small volume of reagents, which makes the method sustainable and suitable for mass production and its versatility has been proved to fabricate microrobots.^[37,38] Fabrication is carried out in two steps. First, liquid droplets are produced inside customized microfluidic chips designed for specific size ranges. The droplets contain all functional components in an alginate matrix that remains liquid by keeping crosslinking agents inaccessible to the hydrogel chains. The crosslinking agents are divalent calcium ions that are trapped by a chelation reaction with EDTA. The produced droplets are taken out of the chip, collected, and further functionalized if necessary. Subsequently, the collected emulsion is placed under a static magnetic field to align the embedded superparamagnetic particles (1 μm diameter), and then, upon a pH shift to acidic, the calcium ions are released from the chelation resulting in immediate ionic crosslinking and structure fixation. These soft capsules behave as microrobots when placed under rotational (1–5 Hz) magnetic fields (5–30 mT) as they roll in a direction perpendicular to the magnetic field rotation axis. Therefore, we steer the soft-capsule microrobots, integrated with functional components for imaging, and cargo transport and release, through precise trajectories with tunable speed (**Figure 1a,i–ii**; details on the fabrication process can be found in the Experimental Section, Video S1 and Figure S1, Supporting Information).

The microfluidic chip design advantageously stabilizes droplet production with high throughput. The design allows for a preferable droplet production with a diameter equal to the hydraulic diameter (\varnothing_H) of the outlet channel, maintaining the constriction ratio in the nozzle (5:8) and the square cross section in the rest of the channels. The four different microfluidic chips were fabricated to produce microrobots with diameters ranging from ≈ 20 to 120 μm (**Figure 1b,i–v**, and **S2a–c**, Supporting Information). The structure of the soft capsule obtained can be observed by optical microscopy and cryo-scanning electron

Figure 1. Fabrication and characterization. a) Schematic of the strategy to fabricate rolling soft microrobots with embedded customizable functional materials (i). The strategy is based on pH-triggered alginate hydrogel gelation to fix the structure of the microrobots (ii). b) Optical microscopy images of SU-8 negatives, showing the nozzles with \varnothing_H of 20, 40, 80, and 120 μm (i–iv, respectively). (v) Particle diameter after microfluidic production for the different \varnothing_H . (vi) 20 μm diameter microrobots with aligned magnetic particles fixed within their structure and imaged by optical microscopy. (vii) 100 μm diameter microrobots imaged by cryo-SEM. c) Superposition of SEM image and EDS mapping (Cl, Ca, Fe, and F) of the microrobots showing homogeneous distribution of the elements over the entire volume of the microrobots (insets: Fe, C, and Ca mapping, respectively). d) 100 μm diameter microrobot being constricted while passing through a glass capillary with inner diameter of 60 μm and being completely reconstituted into its spherical shape after constriction. e) Stiffness evaluation of alginate particles employing AFM, resulting an average young modulus of $\approx 12.4 \pm 8.8$ kPa.

microscopy (cryoSEM) as displayed in Figure 1b.vi–vii, respectively. Furthermore, the resulting microrobots were subjected to energy dispersive spectrometry (EDS) mapping, revealing a

uniform distribution of the constituent materials. The mapping confirmed the presence of carbon (C) derived from the alginic acid chains, the cationic crosslinker calcium (Ca), and

chlorine (Cl) originating from the precursors. Additionally, iron (Fe) was detected, attributable to the incorporation of magnetic microparticles (refer to Figure 1c). The homogeneous distribution of the magnetic particles at the surface of the microrobots can be appreciated in Figure S3a, Supporting Information, where cryoSEM images of a microrobot are presented at different magnifications. To ascertain the alignment and positioning of the magnetic microparticles within the core of the microrobot, cross-sectional analysis was conducted by flash-freezing the samples and utilizing a microtome blade cooled with liquid nitrogen. Then, these sections were analyzed by cryoSEM and EDS, showing the presence of particle chains in both the core of the microrobot and on the surface (Figure S3b,c, Supporting Information).

Alginate is a soft material with similar or lower stiffness compared to some human tissue. As for comparison, the estimated elastic modulus for the female reproductive tissues has been reported to be of around 0.02–1.4 MPa for the uterus and 2.5–30 MPa for vaginal tissue,^[39] making these microrobots excellent candidates for gynecological disease therapies and assisted fertilization, main applications of interest in our group.

The capability of the microrobots to softly interact and adapt with the surrounding geometries was demonstrated by soaking individual microrobots in glass capillaries with different aperture diameters (Figure 1d). Aspiration flow rate regulation was applied to generate a relative negative pressure in the glass capillary that sucks the microrobot nearby. The microrobot briefly stops when it meets a small opening that sits on the top of the opening walls. The part of the microrobot within the diameter of the opening blocks the flow by increasing pressure and deforming to fit into the opening. It was observed that, when the aperture is 0.8 and down to 0.6 times the diameter of the microrobot, the latter is completely soaked into the capillary (Figure 1d). When successfully soaked in, a later positive pressure is then applied to expulse the microrobot back to the solution for final observation and geometry analysis after deformation (Video S2, Supporting Information). For openings smaller than 0.6 times the diameter of the microrobot, the part of the microrobot facing the outside of the opening bends outward, blocking the passage of the robot into the capillary (Figure 1d and S4a, Supporting Information).

The microrobots that passed through the 60 μm diameter capillaries showed a maximum constriction of 64% of their original cross-sectional area. Despite this, the microrobots were able to reconstitute their spherical shape after being released from the constriction, in a process that took less than a minute. The magnetic response and steerability of the microrobots were not affected by the deformation after reconstitution. These results demonstrate the softness potential of these microrobots for use in medical applications, as their stiffness is similar to that of the aforementioned tissues and their capability to regenerate their original shape highlights their susceptibility to adapt to constricted channels.

To further investigate the stiffness of the alginate beads, we employed atomic force microscopy (AFM) to obtain force/distance curves that were to calculate the Young's moduli as detailed in the Experimental Section. The Young's moduli of the alginate beads ranged from 10 to 35 kPa, with a mean value of 12.4 kPa and a standard deviation of 8.8 kPa (Figure 1e and S4b–d, Supporting Information).

2.2. Microrobot Motion Performance Characterization under Optical Feedback Magnetic Control

To characterize the performance of the microrobot, we conducted a parametric study using a combination of electromagnetic coils and optical feedback. The application of an external magnetic field induces a collective magnetic polarization in the embedded chains of magnetic particles. Consequently, when exposed to a rotating magnetic field, the microrobot undergoes a torque that aligns it with the field^[30,40] and enables synchronized movement (Video S3a, Supporting Information). In cases where the microrobot comes into contact with a surface and the rotation axis is perpendicular to that surface, it exhibits a rolling motion. If the rotation is along an axis parallel to the surface, no displacement will occur (Figure 2a).

In order to comprehensively characterize their motion performance, microrobots with diameters of 20, 50, 80, and 100 μm were introduced into different sealed microchambers. A real-time closed-loop control algorithm was initiated to keep the microrobots continuously tracing a defined trajectory. It obtains a microscopic image and uses template matching to localize the microrobot. Based on the difference to the target point, the rotational axis of the magnetic field is adjusted, so the microrobot moves in the target's direction. This process is repeated with a period of ≈ 100 ms. If the microrobot moves close to the target point, it is updated to follow a figure-8 trajectory (Figure 2b). An example of a single repetition of the trajectory is shown in Figure 2c with overlapping images of the microrobot at representative positions (representative records in Video S3b, Supporting Information). The magnetic field rotation frequency was varied from 0.4 to 5 Hz in 0.2 Hz increments every three cycles. The overall experiment time exceeded 10 h of continuous motion for performing 75 cycles in total, thus demonstrating the reproducibility of real-time closed-loop control for actuating the suggested microrobots (Figure 2d and S5a,b, Supporting Information). The acquired coordinates of the microrobot location were used to calculate the displacement velocity, and the velocities over three cycles were averaged for each frequency. It was observed that the speed of the microrobot increases with rotational frequency until the maximum step-out frequency is reached and then steeply decreases. From this, we claim that there is an optimal magnetic field frequency for which microrobots of a specific size will have a maximum velocity. For instance, the maximum velocity reached was 8.3 ± 0.9 , 14.1 ± 3.5 , 15.6 ± 12.4 , and $15.1 \pm 12.2 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ for 20, 40, 80, and 100 μm microrobots, respectively. The step-out frequency is a function of the microrobot diameter, the fluid and microrobot density, the electrostatic forces between the microrobot and the surface, the applied magnetic field strength, and the viscosity of the medium. For the microrobots with diameters of 20, 40, 80, and 100 μm , the step-out frequency found experimentally was 4.4, 2.6, 1.4, and 1.4 Hz, respectively. The tracking error of the closed-loop control system was calculated as the root-mean-squared distance from the ideal trajectory at a rotation frequency of 1 Hz. The results showed errors of ± 17.0 , 14.5, 10.5, and 13.0 μm , with standard deviations of 0.313, 0.578, 0.409, and 0.686 μm , respectively, for the aforementioned sizes of microrobots. These errors correspond to 0.85, 0.36, 0.13, and 0.13 body

Figure 2. Motion trajectory and optical feedback control. a) Extracted frames, every 2.3 ms, of a video (representative clips in Video S3b, Supporting Information) recording an alginate microrobot under magnetic fields rotating parallel to the surface. b) Scheme of the real-time closed-loop control with optical feedback when using magnetic fields rotating perpendicularly to the surface. c) Superimposed images of a 40 μm diameter microrobot tracing a figure-8 trajectory, during an automated experiment using real-time closed-loop control. d) Superimposed path of a microrobot outlining 72 times the figure-8 trajectory. e) Force diagram of the rotating microrobot and mathematical expression of its velocity. f) Average velocity of microrobots with different sizes depending on the rotational frequency (i) and average velocity of 100 μm diameter microrobots in media with different viscosities depending on the rotational frequency (ii). The shaded region represents the standard deviation across the assessed parameters.

lengths, respectively. Notably, the tracking error for all microrobots remains below one body length, although it increases as the microrobot size decreases. The capability of the system to track the microrobots over complex trajectories was showcased by tracing different shapes as shown in Video S3c, Supporting Information.

To better understand the forces involved in the locomotion of the proposed microrobot, we suggest an analytical model.

We assume, the capsule microrobots are microspheres of radius R which rotate with an angular velocity ω along an axis close and parallel to a solid glass surface. Therefore, its motion is described by the quasistatic Stokes equations.^[41] As the inertia is neglected in low Reynolds number environments, the external forces on the sphere are balanced in each direction. In the vertical direction, the gravitational force F_G is balanced with the repulsive F_{rep}

and lifting F_L forces, making the microrobot reach a steady state at a height of h_0 from the bottom surface (Figure 2e). In the horizontal direction, the rotating microrobot generates a propulsion force F_p , which is balanced with the drag force of the fluid F_D when the microrobot translates. Therefore, the following force balance equation can be formulated:

$$\begin{cases} F_G = F_{\text{rep}} + F_L \\ F_D = F_p \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

For the balance of forces in the vertical direction:

$$F_G = \frac{4}{3}\pi(\rho_\mu - \rho_f)R^3g \quad (2)$$

$$F_{\text{rep}} = 4\pi\epsilon\epsilon_0RK\nu_\mu\nu_s e^{-\kappa h_0} \quad (3)$$

$$F_L = \pi\rho_f R^3\omega V \quad (4)$$

where ρ_f and ρ_μ are the density of the fluid and the microrobot, respectively, g is the gravitational constant, $\epsilon\epsilon_0$ is the permittivity of the medium, κ^{-1} is the Debye length, ν_μ and ν_s are the zeta potential of the capsule microrobot and the bottom surface, respectively, and V is the velocity of the microrobot. The considered values are mentioned in the Experimental Section. The distance h_0 between the microrobot and the surface can be calculated by

$$h_0 = -\frac{1}{\kappa} \ln\left(\frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi(\rho_\mu - \rho_f)R^3g - \pi\rho_f R^3\omega V}{\pi\epsilon\epsilon_0RK\nu_\mu\nu_s}\right) \quad (5)$$

For the balance of forces in the horizontal direction: When the microrobot rotates, a propulsion force F_p is generated, and a drag force F_D arises when the microrobot moves in translation.^[41] These forces are described as follows:

$$F_D = 6\pi VR\left(\frac{8}{15}\ln\frac{R}{h_0} + 0.9588\right) \quad (6)$$

$$F_p = 6\pi R^2\omega\left(\frac{2}{15}\ln\frac{R}{h_0} - 0.2526\right) \quad (7)$$

As these two forces are balanced, the velocity of the microrobot when rotating is

$$V = \omega R\left(\frac{\frac{2}{15}\ln\frac{R}{h_0} - 0.2526}{0.9588 + \frac{8}{15}\ln\frac{R}{h_0}}\right) \quad (8)$$

According to this equation, when the rotational angular velocity of the microrobot is synchronized with the rotational frequency of the magnetic field, the motion speed of the microrobot can be calculated for a given magnetic field frequency. However, when the rotational frequency of the magnetic field exceeds a certain threshold (step-out frequency), magnetic momentum transfer becomes incomplete, resulting in a step-out phenomenon.^[42] This model is applicable for magnetic field frequencies below the step-out one; in cases above the step-out frequency, the microrobot may experience slewing, causing a decrease in motion speed and efficiency, making its behavior difficult to predict.

According to our mathematical model, the influence of the viscosity on the velocity of the microrobots is relatively small and leads to a decrease in velocity for the same rotational frequencies when the viscosity increases. The size variation leads to a similar behavior for smaller microrobots' diameters. This effect might be due to the additional hydrodynamic resistance and increased drag experienced by the microrobot when the media's viscosity increases or the microrobot's diameter decreases, respectively. As expected, the experimental results show that when microrobots of the same size ($\varnothing = 100 \mu\text{m}$) are immersed in media with different viscosities, there is a shift in the step-out frequency to slightly higher frequencies and a decrease of the maximum velocity as the viscosity of the media increases. Experimentally, the viscosity was varied by dissolving methylcellulose at two concentrations (0.2 and 0.4% w/v) to mimic the rheological properties of various biological fluids such as oviduct fluid (our intended application scenario). Correspondingly, when decreasing microrobot sizes ($\varnothing = 100, 80, 40, \text{ and } 20 \mu\text{m}$) or increasing viscosity, the experimental data show the expected trend of shifting the step-out frequencies to higher ones while reducing the maximum velocity achieved. To further elucidate the influence of fluid flow rate on the propulsion velocity of our microrobots, we placed our microrobots in sealed microchannels connected to a precision pressure pump at one end. We then applied closed-loop control mechanisms to guide the microrobots in linear trajectories, both against (upstream) and with (downstream) the fluid flow, as documented in Figure S6a and Video S4, Supporting Information. The experiment involved varying the fluid flow rates by adjusting the pressure settings of the pump to 10, 10.5, and 11 mBar, corresponding to flow velocities of $\approx 6.14, 6.44, \text{ and } 6.75 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$, respectively. Our observations confirmed that microrobot velocities were consistently higher when moving downstream than upstream at all pressures tested. Notably, as we incrementally increased the pressure, indicating higher flow rates, we observed a proportional increase in the downstream velocity of the microrobots and a corresponding decrease in their upstream velocity. This direct correlation between the set flow rates and the resulting changes in microrobot velocity is shown quantitatively in Figure S6b, Supporting Information. The comparison of the mathematical model versus the experimental results for the variation viscosities and microrobots sizes are presented in Figure 2f,i-ii, Supporting Information. The analytical model provides valuable insight into the velocity of microrobots, which depends on factors such as their diameter, the viscosity of the medium, and the rotation frequency. The integration of closed-loop control and analytical modeling together provides an early foundation for the development of AI-controlled medical microrobots. The integration of these technologies is expected to lead to improved precision and targeted performance, increased motion efficiency, reduced possibility of error, and personalized treatment options.^[43]

2.3. Microrobots for Dual US-PA Imaging

US imaging is a mature and well-established technology in clinical practice for diagnostic purposes. Compared to other conventional techniques, US provides deep penetration and high

spatiotemporal resolution with minimum adverse effects on biological tissues. However, the biggest microrobot size shown in the current work is at the limit of the technique's spatial resolution ($\approx 100\ \mu\text{m}$), making it challenging not only to detect single microrobots but also to distinguish them from the surrounding tissue. To enhance US contrast in medicine, contrast agents are injected. These contrast agents are typically microbubbles that act as echo-enhancers. However, the stability of these microbubbles is typically a few minutes ($< 10\ \text{min}$) in vivo for medically approved formulations.^[44–46] The instability of microbubbles used as contrast agents is primarily attributed to coalescence caused by collisions, convection, and US-induced oscillations, and dissolution, which is affected by gas solubility, shell permeability, and pressure fluctuations in the surrounding media.^[47] Encapsulation of these US contrast agents would provide protection against interagent collisions and media fluctuations, whereas this supporting matrix reduces convection and gas solubility.

Our approach to improve US contrast consists of the integration of a liquid US contrast agent within the microrobot structure. This strategy also increases the stability of the contrast agents, which are protected by the surrounding hydrogel capsule. The fact that the capsule is soft enables the agents to continue behaving as echo-enhancers. We opted for a phase-change contrast agent which is synthesized as a liquid microdroplet emulsion and become gaseous microbubbles under US excitation (details in the Experimental Section). This methodology brings enhanced stability as it is kept in a liquid state until imaging, being stable for ≈ 2 weeks, while it remains with a similar formulation as the aforementioned medically approved contrast agents. We synthesized the microdroplets using Li's method^[48] which relies on the perfluoropentane (PFP) oil microdroplet nucleation upon the addition of an aqueous solution to decrease the solvent efficacy (schematic in Figure 3a,i; details in the Experimental Section). The size of the microdroplets can be tuned while adjusting the reagent's concentration. We opted for an average microdroplet size of $1\ \mu\text{m}$, measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS), to allow its easy identification by optical microscopy (Figure 3a,ii). The obtained microdroplets resuspended in deionized (DI) water and placed in our experimental setup for imaging exhibit enhanced US contrast compared to a control sample consisting of DI water only (Figure 3a,iii).

As mentioned above, functional components can be easily incorporated within the soft capsule microrobots before the droplet formation by mixing them with alginate hydrogel precursor as a dispersed phase. The aforementioned PFP microdroplets and magnetic particles were embedded in the microrobots for imaging purposes using both US and PA. Due to the small sizes of the microdroplets, the curvature of the hydrogel capsules, and the minimum difference between the alginate and PFP refraction indexes (1.37 and 1.33, respectively), was difficult to directly observe the PFP microdroplets within the microrobot.^[49,50] However, it becomes possible to observe their impact when imaging the microrobots using US imaging. CryoSEM consistently revealed the presence of cavities in samples where PFP microdroplets were integrated (refer to Figure 3b). These cavities are thought to arise during the preparation steps for characterization, particularly due to the freezing effects on the various materials. Moreover, numerous chains of magnetic particles

are directly observable within the microrobot's structure (see Figure 3c).

In our study, we utilized a hybrid imaging system that synergistically combined US and PA imaging techniques to enable comprehensive functional and structural imaging of mobile microrobots, achieving an in-plane resolution of $75\ \mu\text{m}$ and a temporal resolution of 5–20 fps. US imaging provided real-time structural information, particularly in deep tissues. Conversely, PA imaging was employed to obtain molecular data, enhancing the specificity of microrobot tracking, especially when operating within scattering tissues. We employed distinct contrast agents to optimize contrast and resolution for both US and PA modalities: gas-filled particles for US imaging and magnetic particles, also used for microrobot steering, for PA imaging. To compare the imaging effect of these functional materials, three different samples were prepared: pure alginate capsules, alginate capsules with magnetic particles, and the complete microrobots (alginate capsules with magnetic particles and the PFP microdroplets). Each sample was positioned within our setup to undergo PA and US imaging, and corresponding images were acquired (refer to the Experimental Section and Figure S7a,b, Supporting Information). Figure 3d demonstrates static imaging of the three samples, allowing a comparison between optical, US, and PA imaging modes (comparison to the control under optical microscopy in Figure S8a, Supporting Information). The samples are illuminated with an excitation wavelength of 910 nm and the measurements are performed with a position-fixed transducer (21 MHz) to avoid image distortion. Like the control, pure alginate capsules show no contrast by any of the imaging techniques due to their high-water content composition ($\approx 99\%$ water and 1% alginic acid molecular network), making them indistinguishable from the surroundings even for optical microscopy when observing through the tubing. On the other hand, when magnetic particles are added, the microrobots can be observed inside the tubing by optical microscopy due to the accumulation of particles inside the alginate capsules. More importantly, PA contrast is also exhibited in this sample. This signal is directly correlated with the addition of magnetic particles as shown in Figure S8b, Supporting Information. Consistently, by combining magnetic particles and PFP microdroplets, the microrobot is observed by both imaging modalities: US and PA imaging.

The dynamic dual US/PA tracking in real time of such microrobots was also demonstrated. The microrobots were actuated by rotating magnetic fields ($10\ \text{mT}$, $f = 1\ \text{Hz}$) during imaging. The imaging setup was integrated with a coil system to actuate the microrobots in a controlled manner. The sample was prepared and placed in our imaging experimental setup and a video was recorded for the three imaging modalities (Video S5, Supporting Information). A swarm of microrobots (≈ 20 microrobots with $40\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter) was located at an initial position P_0 and then moved to a second position P_1 by the external magnetic field ($10\ \text{mT}$, $1\ \text{Hz}$). After 50 s, the direction of rotation was inverted to move the swarm back to the initial position P_0 . Selected frames of the video showing the dynamic tracking of a swarm of microrobots are shown in time-lapse images in Figure 3e.

The stability of the contrast agents was tested over time using two different experimental setups. First, the contrast signal for both US and PA was observed and analyzed continuously for

Figure 3. US/PA imaging. a) Schematic of the synthesis of PFP microdroplets used as US contrast agents (i), their size distribution by DLS (ii) and optical microscopy (inset), and the comparison of US contrast for water and PFP microdroplets (iii). b) Cryo-SEM image of the cavities (highlighted in cyan) found in microrobots fabricated with PFP microdroplets. c) Cryo-SEM image of the aligned magnetic particles (highlighted in red) within the microrobot. d) Representative optical, US, and PA images were obtained for samples of alginate capsules containing different materials. e) Extracted frames of simultaneous videos recording the movement of a swarm of microrobots, actuated by rotating magnetic fields, from P_0 to P_1 and backward by both US and PA imaging. f) Optical, US, and PA signals acquired after 0, 90, and 180 min of the stability test by periodic excitation of PA.

15 min while both US waves from the transducer and laser pulses were continuously exciting the sample. The sample was illuminated for the US, PA, and optical microscopy imaging to see the change in their contrast (Figure S9a, Supporting Information). A second experiment was conducted with a more

clinically relevant approach, using periodic excitation. In this case, the US was continuously exciting the microrobots but the laser was activated periodically to corroborate the US imaging. Here, the experiment was performed over 3 h with the PA laser being activated every 15 min for 50 s each time

(representative snapshots can be seen in Figure 3f and S9b, Supporting Information). Both experiments demonstrated a similar behavior of the contrast agents under real imaging conditions: no significant decay over time was observed in the PA signal intensity in areas that exhibited PA contrast (Figure S9c, Supporting Information). However, there was a slight increase in the US signal observed in specific regions, which correlated with the presence of bubbles inside the tubing as confirmed by optical microscopy images. As the tubing was filled with the sample dispersed in water and sealed, and the appearance of bubbles only occurred in areas exposed to both US waves and the laser beam, it can be inferred that the formation and expansion of bubbles were a result of the gas release from the encapsulated US contrast agents within the alginate capsules. These bubbles continued to grow over time. However, it is not anticipated that the liberation of the biocompatible organic PFP gas from the microrobots would cause a cytotoxic effect, as it is metabolically inert.^[51] These results proved that the contrast agents, both US and PA, are stable for a reasonable time (≈ 3 h) to perform medical procedures while continuously imaging the microrobots.

In conclusion, we effectively employed safe and complementary imaging techniques, namely, US and PA imaging, to visualize the microrobots by incorporating suitable contrast agents. The combination of these imaging modalities enabled continuous tracking of the microrobots throughout the imaging process. It is worth noting that the selected contrast agents demonstrated excellent stability for at least 3 h of continuous imaging. Overall, these findings emphasize the potential of the microrobots presented in this study for future medical therapies in *in vivo* settings.

2.4. Microrobots' Biocompatibility, Biodegradability and Drug-Delivery Function

Ensuring excellent biocompatibility is crucial when selecting building materials for future medical microrobots. Emphasis should be placed on materials that do not induce harm or immune reactions within the body. Additionally, it is important to consider materials that can be safely eliminated from the body following microrobot-assisted medical treatments. In this study, we conducted an analysis of the cytotoxic effects associated with the various materials employed in the proposed multifunctional microrobots. These materials are encapsulated within an alginate matrix, which serves the dual purpose of enhancing stability and minimizing their interaction with the surrounding environment. This, in turn, mitigates the potential for cytotoxic effects.

An MTS cell proliferation assay was performed with six different samples to determine the cytotoxic effect of each of the components of the microrobot structure with Madin–Darby canine kidney (MDCK) cells. Tetrazolium salt is used to assess the number of metabolically active cells in the medium. This salt is reduced by cells to a colored formazan, resulting in a measurable change in the color of the medium that can be quantified by absorbance. The magnitude of this change is directly proportional to the number of cells in the sample. The first sample consisted of pure alginate capsules in which no significant decrease in cell proliferation is expected, as alginate is a well-known,

widely studied biocompatible material and is often used as a scaffold for cell growth and biomaterials.^[35,52] The magnetic particles functionalized with streptavidin were assessed in two concentrations (8.5×10^8 and 3.5×10^9 particles mL^{-1}) to corroborate the effect of the material and its concentration on the cytotoxicity of the sample. To evaluate the effect of the microdroplets used as US contrast agents, a sample with 10^{10} microdroplets mL^{-1} was prepared and, finally, a sample with the complete microrobots (alginate capsule with 3.5×10^9 magnetic particles mL^{-1} and 10^{10} microdroplets mL^{-1}) was analyzed. A sixth sample containing MDCK cells and medium was used as a control. The samples were incubated for 24 h and the absorbance of the medium was measured and correlated with the normalized cell number (Figure 4a). There were no significant differences in cell number found among the assessed samples, suggesting that the composition of the microrobots presented here is biocompatible.

The *in vivo* scenarios will require strategies to remove the microrobots from the organism. Retrieving them intact is unlikely. Alternatively, degrading them could facilitate their elimination by the body's natural detoxification or clearance mechanisms. Thus, alginate exhibits excellent degradability under certain experimental conditions. For instance, reversible crosslinking could be achieved by competitive chelation or pH change, which requires additional chemicals or a harsh acidic environment that can only work on specific organs. Another option is the enzymatic cleavage of alginate chains by alginate lyase. Humans and mammals in general are lacking this enzyme. Fortunately, this makes the alginate matrix stable for long periods but would demand the administration of the enzyme degrading solution through injection to the site of interest. Another approach would be the incorporation of enzyme-loaded nanocarriers outside or inside the alginate capsules to trigger the degradation at the desired time and location using an additional stimuli.^[53]

To assess the effect of the enzyme on the degradation of the microrobots, first, we analyzed the effect of the enzyme (alginate lyase) in solution when being in close contact with the microrobots. The degradation rate of the microrobots depends directly on the enzyme concentration. Representative images showing the progressive degradation of a $100 \mu\text{m}$ diameter microrobot under the action of 10^{-6} units mL^{-1} of enzyme for 24 h are shown in Figure 4b (time-lapse images taken every hour in Video S6, Supporting Information). Moreover, the ability of the alginate matrix to temporarily retain molecules in its aqueous phase makes this material appealing for the encapsulation of cells and therapeutic cargoes, which can be then released during the microrobot degradation process.^[21] As a drug model, doxorubicin hydrochloride (DOX) was incorporated into the precursor solution before the microfluidic production at a concentration of ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Subsequently, $100 \mu\text{m}$ microrobots were produced, dispersed in cell media, enzymatically treated with 10^{-6} units mL^{-1} , and observed continuously for 24 h. During this period, the microrobots degraded progressively, releasing the auto-fluorescent drug (Figure 4c and Video S6, Supporting Information).

To evaluate the cytotoxic effect of the enzyme and the resulting by-products after degradation, a second MTS assay was performed. Four samples were incubated with MDCK cells for 24 h. The first sample contained microrobots, the second

Figure 4. Biodegradability and biocompatibility analysis. a) MDCK cell number after 48 h incubation with alginate capsules containing different functional materials in the MTS assay. b) Representative images of the biodegradation process of a 100 μm-diameter microrobot under the enzymatic action of alginate lyase. c) Representative images of the drug release (DOX) process by the enzymatic degradation of a 100 μm-diameter microrobot. d) MDCK cell number after 48 h incubation with alginate microrobots and/or enzyme in the MTS assay. e) Representative images of the degradation of a 100 μm-diameter microrobot loaded with AlgL-Psomes under basic conditions (pH 8). f) Schematic illustration of microrobots loaded with AlgL-Psomes and their degradation triggered by a pH shift to basic. g) Representative images of the microrobot's debris (FITC Green), cell nucleus (DAPI Blue), and dead cells (PI Red) after 24 h incubation with or without enzyme. Error bars correspond to the standard deviation over three repetitions per condition for (a) and (d).

contained enzyme (10^{-6} units mL^{-1}), the third contained both microrobots and enzyme, and the fourth sample contained cell medium only as a control. After incubation, the degradation of the microrobots in the third sample was confirmed by optical microscopy. The samples were incubated for a further 24 h and the absorbance was measured to calculate the number of

cells (Figure 4d). The full method is described in the Experimental Section. Again, microrobots alone did not result in a significant decrease in cells number. The sample incubated with enzyme showed a slight decrease in cell number, but this was not statistically significant. The sample with microrobots and enzyme showed a similar decrease in cell number, which,

according to the trend observed, could be attributed more to the amount of enzyme than to the alginate by-products. These results suggest the correct choice of materials for the microrobots, but the degradation process should be optimized to reduce the interaction between the enzyme and the cells.

One approach to reduce the amount of enzyme introduced into the organism is to encapsulate it directly into the microrobot, but direct contact of the enzyme with the alginate would lead to immediate degradation, preventing the formation of the microrobot. To limit the access of the enzyme to the alginate, we prepared enzyme-loaded polymersomes (AlgL-Psomes), in particular, pH-sensitive and photo-crosslinked polymeric vesicles were used in which the enzyme was incorporated via *in situ* loading during self-assembly. This approach ensured that the enzyme was mainly located in the lumen and the membrane.^[54,55] To demonstrate their use, microrobots containing AlgL-Psomes and fluorescent particles were prepared and incubated at pH 8 (details in the Experimental Section). It was observed that the microrobots were completely degraded after only 4 h (Figure 4e and Video S6, Supporting Information). This rapid degradation can be attributed to the enzyme pre-concentration and stabilizing effects provided by the AlgL-Psomes. Embedding the AlgL-Psomes inside the microrobots facilitates faster access to the internal structure (substrate), leading to homogeneous degradation of the microrobots from the inside (the schematic of this process is shown in Figure 4f). In contrast, the initial method, where the enzyme is present in the immediate vicinity of the microrobot, presents limitations to the diffusion process and consequently results in slower degradation. Although the incorporation of these nanodevices has demonstrated promising effectiveness in the degradation of the microrobots, further optimization is necessary to attain better control over the enzymatic digestive activity. Specifically, the development of polymeric vesicles that respond to more suitable stimuli is imperative. This would enable the enzyme to remain inactive during the required period of medical application and be activated on demand when needed. Such an approach would significantly enhance the therapeutic potential of biodegradable microrobots and will be duly explored in future studies, tailored to the specific intended applications.

The proposed release mechanism goes beyond relying solely on the slightly acidic pH characteristic of tumor cells. Instead, it capitalizes on the pH variations present in specific physiological environments. In our study, DOX was used as a model drug to demonstrate the feasibility of encapsulating and delivering molecules on-demand. However, depending on the organ where the microrobots are deployed, the presence of a pH gradient could offer opportunities for targeted drug release. One potential application for microrobots lies in gynecological healthcare, where the female reproductive tract exhibits a pH gradient. For instance, the vaginal pH is relatively low (\approx pH 4.42), while the pH gradually increases toward the Fallopian tubes (\approx pH 7.94).^[56] This pH gradient creates an environment suitable for pH-sensitive drug release from the microrobots, enabling targeted drug delivery *in vivo* or facilitating assisted fertilization through controlled gamete release. As a proof of concept, enzyme-loaded polymersomes were employed to trigger the degradation of the alginate-based microrobots *in situ* postoperation. Alginate itself does not degrade under physiological conditions or in the presence of

local proteases. The use of polymersomes as nanocarriers for biomedical applications has been extensively explored in the literature. Their chemical composition provides versatility, enabling the incorporation of various stimuli and enhancing the stability and functionality of the cargo. These polymersomes can be engineered to release or activate the degrading enzyme in response to specific stimuli, whether they are external or localized.^[57–59]

The action of the enzyme in the alginate is expected to break the alginic acid into smaller blocks.^[60] In the context of *in vivo* applications, it is anticipated that the debris resulting from microrobot degradation as well as the remaining magnetic particles will be cleared by the immune system over time. The employed magnetic composite particles are made of Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles (composition approved by the FDA^[14,15]) embedded into a polymeric matrix which is expected to degrade and be eliminated through the urine within a few days,^[61] releasing the magnetic Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles that can subsequently be cleared by the immune system.

Moreover, the remaining magnetic particles can serve as functional agents to enhance the effectiveness of the intended medical treatment, for example, for penetrating biological barriers or to realize local magnetic hyperthermia. As a demonstration, we present a video illustrating the magnetic steering of debris left by degraded microrobots (Video S7, Supporting Information). This concept is in line with the field of nanorobot swarms, where external magnetic fields enable precise control and manipulation of particles.^[62,63] These remaining magnetic particles can navigate through intricate anatomical structures, facilitating targeted delivery of therapeutics and can be retrieved back using, for example, a magnetic catheter as has been demonstrated elsewhere.^[64]

A cell viability assay was conducted to evaluate the potential cytotoxicity of the degradation products derived from the microrobots on MDCK cell cultures. To accomplish this, microrobots with a diameter of 100 μ m were fabricated and incubated for 24 h with the enzyme at varying concentrations (10^{-5} , 10^{-6} , 10^{-7} , and 10^{-8} units mL⁻¹). As part of our experimental design, multiple control groups were simultaneously evaluated, including samples without cells, enzymes, and/or microrobots, ensuring the validity of our findings. The detailed list of the controls and their preparation can be found in the Experimental Section. The shape and/or integrity of 100 μ m diameter microrobots was tracked using green fluorescent particles embedded in the alginate capsule. The presence of MDCK cells was confirmed using a 4',6-Diamidin-2-phenylindol, dihydrochloride (DAPI) fluorescent staining, a membrane-permeable dye that binds to DNA, including genomic DNA, within intact nuclei of cells. PI is a dye nonpermeable to intact cell membranes. This dye increases its quantum yield significantly when bound to DNA and was used to track large DNA aggregates such as dead cells as their membrane is permeabilized. Brightfield imaging was used to support fluorescent images of DAPI (blue) and PI (red), and their overlay. In all conditions, a uniform cell distribution is observed in the 2D culture by the fluorescence of DAPI and the brightfield images. Because of the proper growth of cells in all control samples and the negligible PI signal indicating the absence of permeabilized cells, we can conclude that the mortality rate is nonsignificant in all conditions. This emphasizes the absence of significant adverse effects from the alginate lyase enzyme

on an MDCK 2D cell culture and its good specificity toward alginate digestion. When no enzyme is present, the structure of the microrobots remains intact, but when an enzyme is added, scattered debris and/or reduced-in-size microrobots are observed on the 2D cell culture after 24 h. These results demonstrated the degradation of the microrobots in vitro under physiological conditions and in the presence of MDCK cells. Selected images of these results are shown in Figure 4g. Representative images from every control and enzyme concentration tested are presented in Figure S10a,b, Supporting Information, respectively.

In order to assess the therapeutic potential of the proposed microrobots, we investigated their ability to transport and release drugs. Our experiments aimed to determine whether the

released drug could effectively enhance the localized mortality of HeLa cells (cervical cancer). To evaluate the efficacy of DOX-loaded microrobots, a live/dead assay was conducted. HeLa cells were incubated and subsequently exposed to various samples to examine the impact of DOX released by the microrobots. The samples investigated included: sample 1 consisting of only HeLa cells as the control group, sample 2 consisting of HeLa cells with the enzyme present, sample 3 involving HeLa cells with the microrobots, sample 4 comprising HeLa cells with both microrobots and the enzyme, sample 5 consisting of HeLa cells with DOX-loaded microrobots, and sample 6 consisting of HeLa cells with both DOX-loaded microrobots and the enzyme. These different sample configurations were analyzed to assess

Figure 5. Biodegradability and biocompatibility analysis. a) Representative images of the microrobot's debris (DOX Dark red), live cells (SYBR Green), and dead cells (PI Red) after 24 h incubation with and without enzyme for microrobots and DOX-loaded microrobots. b) Following the live/dead staining assay to evaluate the effect of DOX-loaded microrobots on HeLa cells, the findings reveal a significant decrease in cell viability. The error bars represent the standard deviation calculated from three repetitions of the experiment. The percentage of dead cells per sample is visually indicated in red, illustrating the pronounced cytotoxic effect of the DOX-loaded microrobots. c) Cumulative release of DOX over time. Inset: Calibration curve for the fluorescence measured for different amounts of DOX. d) A microrobot effectively tracing the 8-shape figure on top of a HeLa cells monolayer. e) Representative images of live (SYBR Green), and dead (PI Red) HeLa cells (i) intact, and (ii) after a microrobot was actuated atop the cell monolayer.

the effect of the released DOX on HeLa cells under varying conditions. The experimental setup aimed to evaluate the therapeutic potential of the microrobots by determining their ability to enhance the mortality of HeLa cells locally through the controlled release of DOX. A live/dead assay was conducted to measure cell viability and determine the impact of the released DOX on HeLa cells in each sample configuration. Each sample was incubated for 48 h followed by their staining with SYBR Green and PI solutions. Fluorescent images were acquired to visualize the cell viability using the green and red channels, which represent live and dead cells, respectively (Figure 5a and S10a,b, Supporting Information). Further details are provided in the Experimental Section. The analysis of these images revealed a significant increase in cell mortality when the DOX-loaded microrobots were degraded in close proximity to the cells. Interestingly, the percentage of cell mortality in samples containing microrobots and/or enzyme without DOX remained below 10%, indicating that these materials alone have a minimal effect on cell viability. However, when microrobots loaded with DOX were incubated with HeLa cells, a significant increase in cell lethality was observed, with mortality rates exceeding 40%. Furthermore, the combination of DOX-loaded microrobots with the enzyme responsible for their degradation further enhanced the mortality, reaching a peak of 63.5% (Figure 5b). These observations confirm the successful loading and release of DOX from the microrobots, resulting in cytotoxic effects on neighboring cells. The obtained results demonstrate the ability of microrobots to induce a therapeutic response in the surrounding cellular environment, highlighting their promising role in precise and localized drug delivery applications. The drug-release rate was quantified by preparing DOX-loaded alginate microrobots and placing them in a solution with 10^{-4} units mL^{-1} of enzyme to degrade the alginate matrix. The fluorescence emission of the solution was measured in a spectrophotometer and subsequently associated with the amount of DOX present in the solution by making a calibration curve with different concentrations of the model drug. The concentration of DOX in the precursor solution was 1 mg mL^{-1} . The total microrobots produced from $5 \mu\text{L}$ of precursor solution was placed in $995 \mu\text{L}$ of water. From this, we expected a final concentration of $5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of DOX in the solution after degradation. The release profile demonstrated a continuous increase in DOX concentration over the initial 8 h, followed by stabilization (Figure 5c). This correlates with the previously observed increase in cell lethality after 24 h incubation of HeLa cells with degrading DOX-loaded microrobots, indicating that the drug was fully released within this timeframe, allowing sufficient time for its cytotoxic effect. The controlled release of DOX ensures sustained therapeutic levels, enhancing the efficacy of the treatment. Detailed experimental procedures are available in the Experimental Section.

To evaluate the impact of microrobot navigation on cell viability, an additional experiment was conducted using HeLa cell monolayers in a microchannel. Microrobots were guided along an 8-shape trajectory on top of the cells. Figure 5d shows a representative frame from Video S8, Supporting Information, of the microrobot's trajectory. Postactuation viability assessment revealed no significant difference in live and dead cell counts between the control region and the actuated region. Figure 5e compares the cell viability in control and actuated areas.

This indicates that the microrobots can traverse cell monolayers without compromising cell viability, demonstrating their potential for safe, targeted drug delivery applications. Our results serve as evidence, demonstrating the feasibility of our method to effectively control and steer microrobots atop living cells, closely resembling real biological tissue. This achievement holds great significance for future medical applications where the microrobots must navigate and interact with biological surfaces.

3. Conclusions

The presented work represents a significant breakthrough in addressing multiple challenges faced in the field of microrobots. Specifically, these challenges include issues related to softness, adaptability, biodegradability, traceability under scattering tissues, and biomedical functionality. These requirements have been successfully addressed through the development of a single microrobot design that effectively caters to these diverse needs.

The utilization of a microfluidic strategy has enabled the continuous and high-throughput production of alginate magnetic capsule microrobots with adjustable sizes ranging from 20 to $120 \mu\text{m}$ with exceptional size monodispersity (monodispersity indexes of 0.11, 0.08, 0.03, and 0.001 to produce 20, 40, 80, and $120 \mu\text{m}$ diameter microrobots, respectively).

The incorporation of a biosourced hydrogel as the building material provides the necessary flexibility to maneuver through narrow passages while also providing adequate structural support for controlled and precise movements. Motion control is achieved through the integration of aligned biocompatible magnetic particles embedded within the microrobot's structure, which can be actuated by external rotating magnetic fields. The closed-loop feedback control of these microrobots has been successfully demonstrated and analyzed by fine-tuning the generated magnetic field, facilitating their precise navigation with real-time correction. This capability allows for continuous operation over extended periods, surpassing 10 h of highly accurate actuation.

Moreover, the adoption of rolling motion of the suggested microrobots, which emulates the locomotion of immunological cells, has proven to be a successful strategy for navigating specific barriers encountered in complex *in vivo* scenarios.

In addition, the dual imaging modality mediated by the integration of US and PA contrast agents is also a significant advancement toward their operation under scattering tissues. Our method of producing gas-filled microbubbles into a soft structure for US contrast is novel and provides greater stability for imaging in contrast to commercially available gas-filled particles (imaging over 3 h of continuous imaging).

The self-contained degradation mechanism is another crucial feature. Unlike previous degradable microrobots that rely on external triggers or high enzyme doses, the here developed microrobots integrates the degrading agent directly, controlled by pH-sensitive polymersomes embedded within the microrobot. This innovation ensures precise, controlled degradation and minimizes potential immune reactions. Finally, the manufacturing process also allows the incorporation of drugs, as evidenced by the effective delivery and increased lethality in target cells demonstrated *in vitro*.

Collectively, these functionalities position these microrobots as highly promising candidates for future in vivo applications. Notably, the careful selection of materials in their design ensured the absence of observed cytotoxic effects in the tests conducted during this study. However, additional investigations are essential to explore possible side effects and comprehensively understand the behavior of the microrobots within living organisms.

Still, rigorous investigations regarding possible side effects and comprehensive assessments of microrobot behavior in vivo are crucial to ensure their safety and efficacy in future applications. The scaling of magnetic fields and imaging penetration from small animals like mice to a human's scale are also important factors to take into consideration. This is because the magnetic field strength diminishes in proportion to the cube of the distance. Consequently, the generation of magnetic fields must be increased by a factor of 100. Achieving this for electromagnets necessitates a 100-fold increment in electrical current and an increase in the number of windings, which, in turn, imposes greater mechanical and thermal loads. Furthermore, the decay of the magnetic field gradient is even more rapid, following the fourth power of the distance. Therefore, a 1000-fold higher field generation is necessary. In human-scale applications, magnetic actuation predominantly relies on torque transfer, as it benefits from more favorable scaling laws compared to gradient-based propulsion.^[12] Current imaging modalities possessing high spatial resolution have either limitations in penetration depth or temporal resolution. However, novel approaches based on dynamic magnetic field mapping, inductive sensing, and/or integrated magnetoresistance sensors used as electronic compasses have shown promising results toward human-scale microrobot's real-time tracking.^[65,66]

With further research and development, these microrobots hold promise for revolutionizing targeted drug delivery, imaging, and precision medicine, opening new avenues for transformative healthcare applications.

4. Experimental Section

US Contrast Agent Formulation: To synthesize the US contrast agent, Li's method of synthesis of phase-change US contrast agents was followed.^[48] First, a lipid solution (3 mL) consisting of 1.144 mM DPPC and 0.057 mM DSPE-PEG2000 in ethanol absolute was prepared in a glass vial. The lipids solution was homogenized using a vortex and then divided into two parts. One part was transferred into a new glass vial and saturated with PFP, drop-by-drop with gentle stirring while cooling the solution on an ice bath. At saturation, a nondissolving drop of PFP is remaining at the bottom of the vial. Then, a 50% w/v PFP-saturated lipid solution was obtained by mixing 1:1 v/v of the saturated solution with the remaining part of the lipid solution. Besides, a solvent solution (2 mL) consisting of DI water, 1,2-propanediol, and glycerol mixed at a 7:2:1 volume ratio was prepared with the purpose of the later PFP solubility decrease. Finally, this solvent solution (2 mL) was rapidly transferred into the glass vial containing 2 mL of 50% w/v PFP-saturated lipid solution during agitation. The mixing of those two solutions led to the nucleation of PFP microdroplets emulsion due to the lower solubility of PFP in the solvent solution. The PFP microdroplet emulsion was protected from coalescence thanks to the surfactant stabilization property of the lipids and the solvents. The obtained emulsion solution was allowed to rest for 15 min to reach equilibrium. Then, the emulsion solution was washed 2 times by centrifugation (620 rcf at 4 °C for 7 min) while discarding the

supernatant and resuspending the PFP microdroplets pellet in DI water. The US contrast agents were then stored at 4 °C until use.

Alginate Hydrogel Precursor Preparation: The gel precursor solution was a 1:1 mixing ratio between a solution of 2% w/v alginate in DI water and a 0.05 M solution of chelated calcium ions (consisting here of CaCl₂ mixed with EDTA in a 1:1 ratio in DI water neutralized with NaOH (7.4 ≤ pH ≤ 7.8)). The final gel precursor solution was thus containing 1% w/v alginate and 0.025 M chelated calcium ions (CaEDTA).

Mixture of Magnetic Particles Mixture and Alginate: The magnetic particles were used as provided by the manufacturer, washed, and redispersed 2 times in DI water. Then, a third washing step was performed to exchange media and redisperse particles in the solution of alginate hydrogel precursor (see above). The final concentration of magnetic particles was 10⁹ particles mL⁻¹ for most of the experiments (also stated as a "high" concentration for biocompatibility assay) or 10⁸ particles mL⁻¹ for the "low" concentration used within the biocompatibility assay.

Preparation of the Liquid Solutions for Microfluidics: Disperse Phase (Droplets): The magnetic particles, the US contrast agents, and the drugs can be added together or separated as required. The addition consists of a similar procedure as the aforementioned for the incorporation of the magnetic particles, by using the alginate hydrogel precursor solution as redispersing media.

Preparation of the Liquid Solutions for Microfluidics: Continuous Phase (Fluorinated Oil): A stock solution of 5% w/v FluoSurf surfactant in HFE-7500 fluorinated oil was created for long-term storage. From this stock, a μL solution at 0.5% w/v FluoSurf was prepared and used as a continuous phase for the droplet generation.

Acetic Acid-Saturated Fluorinated Oil (to Induce Alginate Gelation): Besides the microfluidic continuous phase, a blend of acetic acid oil was prepared as a means to shift the droplet's pH and triggered the alginate crosslinking. The solution consisted of 0.1% w/v of acetic acid in HFE-7500 fluorinated oil with 0.5% w/v FluoSurf.

Microfluidic Device Fabrication and Procedure: Mold for Soft Lithography: The mold, for the microfluidic chip fabrication, was made on a silicon wafer using SU-8 negative resist lithography. First, a common layer to all microfluidic devices, of 20 μm thickness, was patterned using SU-8 2010 on a Mask-aligner MA6 (SUSS MicroTec) using a chromium mask. Then, a second layer was patterned to customize the nozzle dimensions and produce microrobots of different sizes, using the appropriate SU-8 negative resist according to the required thickness of the features (SU-8 2050 or SU-8 2100). The alignment and exposure were performed using mask-less writing on an MLA-100 (Heidelberg Instruments). All the SU-8 lithography was performed following the manufacturer's datasheet.

Microfluidic Device Fabrication and Procedure: Microfluidic Device Assembly: The microfluidic devices were fabricated from the SU-8 mold using poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) and a soft-lithography approach. Briefly, the mold was filled with a 3–5 mm thickness of uncured mix of PDMS elastomer and curing agent in a 10:1 w/w ratio, degassed, and cured on a hotplate at 120 °C for 15 min. After cooling down to room temperature, the PDMS was detached from the mold and the inlets/outlets were created using a 0.75 mm diameter biopsy puncher. The PDMS was then covalently bonded to a 25 × 75 mm microscopy glass slide using oxygen plasma bonding: both glass and PDMS surfaces were exposed to oxygen plasma for 30 s in a vacuum with a flow of 25 sccm of oxygen at 50% power (Femto low-pressure plasma system, Diener). The PDMS and glass slide surfaces were then immediately contacted to seal the microchannels. Finally, the microfluidic chips were treated using a gas-phase silanization process, immediately after plasma bonding: the chips were placed in a vacuum chamber together with two Petri dishes containing, respectively, 30 μL of perfluorosilane and 100 μL of DI water. The vacuum chamber was then pumped down for ≈5 min and the silanization process was held overnight.

Microfluidic Device Fabrication and Procedure: Microfluidic Procedure for Emulsion Synthesis: The microfluidic production of liquid alginate droplets that would later turn into functional microparticles was performed on-chip under an inverted microscope and monitored with a CMOS camera using an exposure time <100 μs to enable the visualization of droplet production.

The microfluidic chip was placed under a microscope, and the microfluidic solutions prepared previously were inserted in 1 mL glass syringes (Hamilton Company) and mounted on a flow controller (neMESYS Low-Pressure Syringe Pump, Cetoni GmbH). All connections between the microfluidic chip, the syringes, and the outlet collection vial were established using PTFE tubing and medical needles (27 G) (Figure S2a, Supporting Information). The chip was first filled with the continuous phase mixture consisting of oil and surfactant to wet all surfaces. Then, the dispersed phase syringe was connected to the chip and the droplet production was started. The flow rate for the dispersed phase was stabilized at $30 \mu\text{L h}^{-1}$ while the continuous phase flow rate was kept between 400 and $800 \mu\text{L h}^{-1}$ to stabilize the production and tune the diameter and production rate of the droplets. Typically, the continuous phase flow rate was set to obtain droplets with a diameter equal to the width of the outlet channel of the chip. For the size comparison, the continuous phase flow rate was fixed at $600 \mu\text{L h}^{-1}$ to have a direct comparison of the influence of the nozzle and outlet channel dimensions. The produced droplets were collected into a plastic vial via PTFE tubing until further processing of the emulsion. For the size histogram, 1000 beads produced by each different chip were measured by analyzing their optical microscopy images in ImageJ. The relative count for each diameter was then plotted to compare the size distribution produced by the chips.

Microrobots Assembly: From Emulsion to Functional Hydrogel Capsules: The structural organization of the magnetic particles and crosslinking of the alginate, to later obtain functional microrobots, were performed off-chip. First, the vial of the previously collected emulsion was placed inside a ring-shaped permanent magnet ($\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$, 20 mT, 1 cm I.D., and 2 cm O.D.) for 1 min until reaching stable columnar organization of the magnetic particles (Figure S2bi, Supporting Information). Then, the alginate crosslinking was induced by the addition of acidic fluorinated oil in a 1:1 volume ratio under gentle stirring, obtaining a structural hydrogel backbone for the microrobots and maintaining the organization of the magnetic particles within the hydrogel (Figure S2bii, Supporting Information). The crosslinking process was held for 2 min at room temperature before breaking the emulsion stability to retrieve the functional microrobots. Then, the emulsion was broken by the addition of a competing weak surfactant (perfluoro-octanol) in a 2:1 volume ratio. After this procedure, the alginate capsules are agglomerated in a big cluster which can be transferred to DI water with a spatula. The sample was redispersed by vortexing and rinsed 3 times by classical centrifugation procedure (dispersion, centrifugation, discard media, and resuspend in fresh media) in a benchtop centrifuge for 30 s. Finally, the microrobot concentration was estimated if necessary using a Neubauer chamber, and a stock solution of 100 microrobots mL^{-1} was established and stored at 4°C .

Actuation and Velocity Analysis: For the actuation, the microrobots were placed in long microchannels with a square cross section of $200 \times 200 \mu\text{m}$. The microrobots were actuated using a magnetic field generating system (MFG-100-i, Magnebotix AG); the experimental setup is illustrated in Figure S5a, Supporting Information. By using rotational magnetic fields, angular momentum is transferred to the magnetic particles, which move the solid structure of the microrobot. If the axis of rotation is vertical, the microrobots rotate at a speed controllable by the frequency of rotation of the magnetic field. In this case, the displacement is negligible. When the axis of rotation is horizontal, the microrobots roll on the surface. The axis of rotation can be varied in any direction from the horizontal plane to drive the microrobot along specific trajectories.

Motion Characterization with Closed-Loop Control: For comprehensively characterizing the motion behavior of the microrobots in an experiment, closed-loop control with optical feedback was employed. A figure-8 trajectory was chosen to keep the object in the viewport while continuously moving it. Automatizing the data acquisition allowed for systematic variation of the parameters and obtaining sufficient data for collecting statistics. The parameters that were varied are rotational frequency (between 0.4 and 5 Hz in steps of 0.2 Hz), particle size ($20\text{--}100 \mu\text{m}$), and the viscosity of the medium (methylcellulose content of 0, 0.2, and 0.4% w/v), while the magnetic field strength was fixed at 30 mT. For each parameter set, at least three full revolutions of the 8-shape were acquired, resulting in a multihour experiment per particle. The tracking of the particle was done

based on images (2592×1994 pixel, 8-bit quantization, 20 Hz frame rate) from a camera (Basler 60ucPRO) connected to the microscope (Nikon Ti2) using a $10\times$ objective. Template matching via 2 d correlation and peak detection is performed on a GPU (Nvidia GeForce RTX 3090, 24 GB) and gives the particle's current position. This is compared to the next point of the planned trajectory and the direction of rotation of the magnetic field is updated.

Mathematical Modeling: The fluid used was DI water and therefore its density ρ_f considered as 997 kg m^{-3} ; the density of the microrobot ρ_μ was considered as the one for the hydrogel matrix composed of alginate 1%, reported as 1.011 g cm^{-3} .^[67] The gravitational constant g is $6.6743 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$, the permittivity of the DI water $\epsilon\epsilon_0$ is $7.16 \times 10^{-10} \text{ F m}^{-1}$, the Debye length κ^{-1} was considered as $76 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}$, the zeta potential for alginate microcapsules ν_μ has been reported as -20 mV , and the one for a glass water interface ν_s is -62 mV . The velocity of the microrobot was averaged as $10 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$.

The distance between the microrobot and the surface h_0 is dependent on the diameter of the microrobot and can be calculated (Table 1). From these values, the velocity can be calculated and plotted for each microrobot's diameter as a function of the frequency.

We fabricated microrobots with diameters ranging from 20 to $120 \mu\text{m}$. Without loss of generality, we can assume:

$$\text{Density of water } (\rho) = 1000 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Velocity of the particle } (\nu) = 20 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Diameter of the particle } (D) = 10^{-6} \text{ m} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Dynamic viscosity of water } (\mu) = 0.001 \text{ Pa s} \quad (12)$$

The characteristic linear dimension for a sphere in fluid dynamics is typically the diameter, which in this case is 10^{-6} m .

With this we can calculate from the Reynolds number equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Re} &= (\rho * \nu * D) / \mu \\ &= (1000 \text{ kg m}^{-3} * 20 * 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1} * 100 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}) / 0.001 \text{ Pa s} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Re} = 0.002 \quad (<< 1!) \quad (14)$$

This low Reynolds number indicates that the motion of the particle is in a highly viscous flow regime. Inertial forces are negligible compared to the viscous forces. If D or ν decreases, Re will decrease even more (e.g., $\text{Re} = 0.001$ if $\nu = 10 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, and $\text{Re} = 0.0004$ if $D = 20 \mu\text{m}$)

Young's Moduli Estimation: The AFM measurements were carried out using a JPK NanoWizard V (JPK Instruments AG, Berlin, Germany) in force spectroscopy mode under liquid conditions. For the measurements, a tipless cantilever beaded with a borosilicate glass sphere of $5 \mu\text{m}$ diameter was used. The spring constant of the tip was 0.1 N m^{-1} , and the resonance frequency was $\approx 30 \text{ kHz}$ (CP-qp-CONT-BSG, sCube, NanoAndMore).

To perform the experiment, a metallic stage with circular cavities was used. A 400 square mesh aluminum grid was affixed into the cavity using double-sided tape. Two microliters of the sample were loaded onto the grid so the beads were "trapped" on the mesh. Subsequently, the cavity was filled with Milli-Q water (Bruker—JPK Instruments AG, Berlin, Germany) (Figure S4c, Supporting Information). The scanning areas

Table 1. Estimated values of h_0 for the microrobots with different diameters.

Diameter of the microrobot [μm]	h_0 [nm]
20	1.98
40	2.03
80	2.14
100	2.34

ranged from 20 to 30 μm , with setpoints around 3 nN. The extension/retract speed was set to 3 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ and the length to 2 μm . A closed loop was used. The obtained force/distance curves were analyzed using the JPK data processing software to calculate the Young's moduli (Figure S4c, Supporting Information).

Softness Test: Glass capillaries of different diameters (20, 40, 60, and 100 μm) were used to assess the ability of microrobots to adapt their shape when constrained through openings smaller than their diameter. To do this, 100 μm diameter microrobots were prepared and placed under the microscope by pipetting a 200 μL drop of microrobots in water onto a glass slide. A dispensing syringe was filled with DI and loaded into the syringe pump. The appropriate glass capillary was then connected to the syringe via PTFE tubing and the tip of the capillary was brought close to a microrobot. The pressure pump was then switched on to apply negative pressure and a video of each microrobot was recorded. When the negative pressure was sufficient to soak the microrobot, a similar amount of positive pressure was applied to eject the microrobot from the capillary. Once in the slide, the microrobot was rotated by magnetic fields to check that its shape remained spherical after compression in the capillary.

US/PA Imaging: The Vevo F2 LAZR-X Multi-Modal Imaging (FUJIFILM VisualSonics, The Netherlands) that allows dual US and PA imaging was used for the *in vitro* experiments. The measurements were carried out using a 256-element linear array US transducer at a central frequency of 21 MHz and the signals were collected and reconstructed using onboard automated postprocessing. The system was also equipped with fiber optic bundles on either side of the US transducer for illumination. The fiber bundle was coupled to a tunable Nd:YAG laser (680–970 nm) with a 20 Hz repetition rate. For single pulse excitation, the PA images were acquired at an excitation wavelength of 915 nm (with in-plane axial (75 μm) and temporal (5–20 fps) resolution. Commercially available methacrylate support (Vevo Phantom, FUJIFILM VisualSonics, The Netherlands) was used to mount transparent intravascular polyurethane tubing (inner diameter $\approx 380 \mu\text{m}$ and outer diameter $\approx 840 \mu\text{m}$, SAI Infusion Technologies, USA) as a fluidic channel for experiments. Figure S7a,b, Supporting Information, depicts the experimental setup. For each condition, a freshly prepared sample of microrobots was filled into a different tubing and mounted in the experimental setup.

For the evaluation of the effect of the different functional materials embedded in the microrobots, four samples were prepared as follows. One tube was filled with DI water as a control. Then, three different samples of alginate capsules were used to analyze which reactant provided the PA signal: one with empty capsules, one with magnetic particles, and the last one with magnetic particles and US contrast agents. The phantoms were fixed in a chamber and submerged in DI water for enhancing the acoustic coupling with the probe.

For the imaging of each sample, the US probe was manually focused on the phantom region of interest and held stationary in a holder. The US images and videos were acquired in bright mode with a 21 MHz probe at a gain of 8 dB. PA images and videos were acquired simultaneously with the US images using the same probe with a PA gain of 40 dB and a laser at 785–910 nm.

Hybrid US/PA Tracking: The previously described setup for US/PA imaging was used to record the microrobots inside an imaging phantom. The microrobots were actuated using an electromagnetic system OctoMag (Magnebotix AG) to generate rotating magnetic fields (20 mT and 1 Hz) to move the microrobots along the phantom tubing. A video was recorded for 50 s with the field rotating in the described direction (Video S3b, Supporting Information). Then, the rotational direction was shifted by 180° to move the microrobots in the opposite direction for 50 s more. The video was then analyzed and the microrobots swarm was tracked manually in postprocessing.

Contrast Signal Stability: Two experiments were performed to demonstrate the stability of the contrast agents inside the microrobots during imaging. In both, the US/PA imaging setup was kept as previously described but coupled with a digital microscope (Keyence VHX-970F) for simultaneous optical feedback. The microrobots were fabricated one day in advance and stored at 4 °C until used.

Contrast Signal Stability: Continuous Excitation: A sample of microrobots was loaded in an imaging phantom and was continuously imaged by both US and PA for 15 min. Two videos were recorded for the complete experiment focused on the same region of interest in the sample where a swarm of microrobots was localized. One video contained the US and PA imaging and a second one for the optical microscopy.

Contrast Signal Stability: Periodic Excitation: In a real-case scenario, the US could be used as a primary method for continuous imaging while PA used as secondary feedback at certain intervals to corroborate the US image. This reduces laser exposure and related risks. Resembling this scheme, a fresh sample of microrobots was imaged continuously by the US and optical microscopy for 200 min. The laser was started every 15 min and kept for 1 min. During this PA excitation period, images were acquired for the same region of interest by the three imaging techniques (US, PA, and optical microscopy).

MTS Assay (Microrobot Components): Five different samples of 100 μm diameter alginate capsules were prepared to evaluate the cytotoxicity of the different reagents in the microrobots as follows: one with empty capsules, one with low magnetic particles concentration (8.5×10^6 particles mL^{-1}), one with high magnetic particles concentration (3.5×10^9 particles mL^{-1}), one with US contrast agents alone, and one with both magnetic particles (high concentration) and US contrast agents. All alginate capsules were used at a concentration of 50 capsules μL^{-1} .

Each sample (100 μL) was incubated with 200 μL of medium and 2500 MDCK cells in different wells of a microtiter plate. After 48 h, 20 μL of MTS were added to each well and the plate was incubated for 2 h more. After this period, the absorbance of each sample was measured on a Spectramax Plus384 microplate reader (Molecular Devices LLC, US) at OD = 490 and correlated with the number of cells. The whole process was carried out at a constant temperature of 37 °C.

Biodegradability: A single sample of 100 μm diameter microrobots was prepared and concentrated at 5 microrobots μL^{-1} . During the preparation, green fluorescent particles ($\varnothing = 200 \text{ nm}$) were embedded in the microrobots for easy monitoring of the degradation rate. Fifteen different wells of a microtiter plate were filled with 95 μL of DI. Gently, 4 μL of the microrobots solution was added to every well. Previously, four enzyme (alginate lyase) concentrations were prepared in DI, and 1 μL was added to different wells to obtain 10^{-3} , 10^{-6} , 10^{-9} , and 10^{-12} units mL^{-1} final concentrations. Each concentration was repeated in triplicate and three wells were left without enzyme as control.

The samples were monitored continuously for 48 h or until the full dissolution of the capsules.

Drug Release: A model drug was prepared by dissolving DOX at 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with the CaEDTA solutions as previously stated for every embedded material in the microrobots. After production, a final concentration of $\approx 50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DOX is loaded in every microrobot. A microrobot's solution is prepared at a concentration of 0.2 microrobots μL^{-1} and 99 μL of this solution is transferred to six different wells of a microtiter plate. A solution of the enzyme Alginate Lyase (AlgL) is prepared at 10^{-4} units mL^{-1} . The microrobots are incubated for 20 min at 37 °C and then 1 μL of the enzyme is added to three wells. 1 μL of DI is added to the remaining three wells as controls. The samples are incubated at 37 °C and images of every well are acquired after 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 24, 48, and 72 h. An inverted fluorescence microscope (Zeiss, Germany) was used, and the fluorescence images were acquired with a filter of 580 nm and 200 ms exposure time.

MTS Assay (Degradation Subproducts): Microrobots of 100 μm diameter with embedded fluorescent particles were prepared. Then, 2500 MDCK cells were seeded with 200 μL of medium in different wells of a microtiter plate. After 24 h, three wells were filled with microrobots, three wells were filled with enzyme, and three wells were filled with both microrobots and enzyme. The final concentration of microrobots and enzyme was 50 microrobots mL^{-1} and 10^{-6} units mL^{-1} , respectively. Three other wells were filled with cell medium only as a control. All samples were incubated for 24 h and microrobot degradation was confirmed in the wells containing microrobots and enzyme; the samples were then incubated for a further 24 h. After this period, 20 μL of MTS reagent were added to each well and the plate was incubated for 2 h. The absorbance of each sample was then

measured in a microplate reader at OD = 490 and correlated with the number of cells. The whole process was carried out at a constant temperature of 37 °C.

Degradation of AlgL-Psomes-Loaded Microrobots: Fabrication of Enzyme-Loaded Polymersomes: AlgL-Psomes were fabricated by the self-assembly of a block copolymer (BCP).

First, the amphiphilic BCP (PEG₄₅-*b*-P(DEAEMA₈₉-*co*-DMIHMA₂₃)) was successfully synthesized by atom transfer radical polymerization.^[54,68] This block copolymer features a methoxy end group at the hydrophilic poly(ethylene glycol) segment, while the hydrophobic part consists of pH-sensitive 2-(diethylamino)ethyl methacrylate (DEAEM) and photocrosslinker, 6-(*N*-(3,4-dimethylmaleinimido))hexyl methacrylate (DMIHMA). The composition, molar mass, and dispersity were well characterized by ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy and size exclusion chromatography. $M_n = 35\,500\text{ g mol}^{-1}$; $M_w = 40\,200\text{ g mol}^{-1}$; PDI = 1.13.

Then, the self-assembly of this BCP was performed using the so-called pH switch method and using the in situ loading approach previously reported.^[54] For this, a solution of 1 mg mL⁻¹ of BCP in 0.01 M HCl (pH 2) was prepared and stirred until the BCP was dissolved. The final solution is passed through a 0.2 μm nylon filter to remove any impurities. In parallel, a solution of enzyme of 1 mg mL⁻¹ was prepared in 1 mM PBS. Afterward, the pH of the BCP solution is increased until pH 5 and then the enzyme was added. Later, the self-assembly process was triggered by increasing the pH slowly to pH 8 through the addition of 1 and 0.1 M NaOH. The final conditions were 1 mg BCP mL⁻¹ and 0.2 mg enzyme mL⁻¹. AlgL-Psomes were formed after 1 day of stirring in dark conditions. The solution was passed through a 0.8 μm nylon filter and then irradiated for 45 s to trigger the crosslinking process (EXFO Omnicure 2000, Lumen Dynamics Group Inc., Canada). Finally, the AlgL-Psomes were dialyzed (1000 kDa) for 24 h against 1 mM PBS to remove the nonloaded enzyme. The hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of purified AlgL-Psomes was studied by DLS (Zetasizer Nanoseries instrument, Malvern Instruments, UK). Z-Average (D_h) = 140 nm.

Degradation of AlgL-Psomes-Loaded Microrobots: Fabrication of AlgL-Psomes-Loaded Microrobots: The solution of AlgL-Psomes was mixed with the alginate precursor solution and fluorescent particles, and immediately used for the microfluidic fabrication of microrobots as described above. CaEDTA or acidic oil was not used to crosslink the alginate as AlgL-Psomes are pH sensitive; instead, the alginate droplets produced were collected and a 0.1 M CaCl₂ solution in DI was added to the oil phase. The sample was gently stirred to allow the alginate to crosslink and the microparticles were recovered from the oil with a spatula. Finally, the microrobots were immersed in 30 μL of perfluoro-octanol to break the emulsion and rinsed three times with DI.

Degradation of AlgL-Psomes-Loaded Microrobots: Degradation: Three wells of a microtiter plate were filled with 95 μL of DI (pH 6.2) and three with 95 μL of a mixture of DI and NaOH (pH 8). 5 μL of the AlgL-Psomes-loaded microrobot solution was added to all wells and the samples were continuously monitored by fluorescence microscopy for 4 h or until the AlgL-Psomes-loaded microrobots degraded.

Cell Viability Assay: A single sample of 100 μm diameter microrobots with embedded green-fluorescent particles was prepared and concentrated at 5 microrobots μL⁻¹. MDCK cells were seeded into 21 wells of a microtiter plate with 96 μL of medium and incubated for 48 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. After this period, a monolayer of MDCK cells was observed at the bottom of every well. Four different enzyme (alginate lyase) solutions were freshly prepared in DI using 100 times the required final concentration.

Eight different conditions were analyzed, each one replicated in triplicate in different wells containing cells (except for Control 4). 3 μL of microrobot's solution and 1 μL of enzyme and/or cell medium were used to complete a 100 μL total volume per well as stated in Table 1 and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ (Table 2).

After this period, 1 μL of DAPI and 1 μL of PI staining solutions were added to every well and incubated for 20 min more. Finally, 75 μL of supernatant was slowly replaced with fresh cell media to remove the excess staining solutions, and images of every well were acquired using an inverted fluorescence microscope (Zeiss, Germany). A fluorescent lamp HXP 120 (Zeiss, Germany) was used and filters for 525, 461, and

Table 2. Experimental conditions for cell viability test.

	Microrobots (3 μL)	Enzyme concentration (1 μL)
Control 1	Yes	No
Control 2	No	No
Control 3	No	Yes (10 ⁻⁶ units mL ⁻¹)
Control 4 ^{a)}	Yes	Yes (10 ⁻⁶ units mL ⁻¹)
Sample 1	Yes	Yes (10 ⁻⁵ units mL ⁻¹)
Sample 2	Yes	Yes (10 ⁻⁶ units mL ⁻¹)
Sample 3	Yes	Yes (10 ⁻⁷ units mL ⁻¹)
Sample 4	Yes	Yes (10 ⁻⁸ units mL ⁻¹)

^{a)}Control 4 was performed in empty wells (without cells) for corroborating the activity of the enzyme without cells.

580 nm were used for FITC, DAPI, and PI, with 50, 40, and 800 ms exposure times, respectively.

Live/Dead Assay for Drug Delivery: DOX-loaded microrobots were prepared as stated before by mixing a known concentration of DOX (1 mg mL⁻¹) in the precursor solution for the microfluidic process. HeLa cells were seeded into 18 wells of a microtiter plate with 200 μL of cell medium and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. After this period, the HeLa cells were exposed to the different components to assess the effect of the DOX released by the microrobots. The tested samples could contain microrobots (with or without DOX) in a concentration of ≈0.1 per μL and/or enzyme (alginate lyase) in a final concentration of 10⁻⁶ units mL⁻¹. The sample formulations were: 1) sample 1: only HeLa cells in cell medium; 2) sample 2: HeLa cells with enzyme; 3) sample 3: HeLa cells with microrobots without DOX; 4) sample 4: HeLa cells with microrobots without DOX end enzyme; 5) sample 5: HeLa cells with DOX-loaded microrobots; and 6) sample 6: HeLa cells with DOX-loaded microrobots and enzyme.

Each sample was repeated by triplicate in different wells. After the inclusion of the microrobots and/or the enzyme, all samples were incubated for 48 h more at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. After this period, 1 μL of SYBR Green and 1 μL of PI staining solutions were added to every well and incubated for 20 min more. Fluorescent images were acquired to visualize the cell viability using the green and red channels, which represent live and dead cells, respectively.

Drug-Release Quantification: The calibration curve was done by diluting different concentrations of DOX (10, 7.5, 5, 2.5, 1, and 0.1 μg mL⁻¹), and each of them was read in the spectrophotometer by triplicated, assigning a concentration amount to the fluorescence values measured (Figure 5c, inset). A linear regression was done for these values so $y = 3083x + 3.5$. Then, DOX-loaded microrobots were prepared from a total volume of 5 μL. The concentration of DOX in the precursor solution is 1 mg mL⁻¹. The total of microrobots produced was washed and placed in an empty well with 995 μL of water. The microrobots were left to sink at the bottom of the well, and the supernatant was taken and measured in a clean well. After reading, the liquid was gently poured back onto the alginate microrobots. This procedure was repeated 3 times. Then, the enzyme alginate lyase was then dissolved at a 10⁻⁴ concentration in the microrobot solution, and fluorescence measurements of the supernatant were taken every 0.5 h for the first 4 h, and then every 2 h for 24 h, following the previously described procedure. All the measurements were performed for fluorescence at a target wavelength of 590 nm (DOX characteristic emission) with a cutoff at 570 nm. Reads were taken from the bottom, with 10 flashes per read in medium sensitivity mode, and repeated by triplicated.

Motion of the Microrobots atop HeLa Cells: A simple long microchannel (1 mm height, 1 mm width, and 3 cm length) was prepared by soft lithography in PDMS and plasma bonded to a glass slide to seal it. The HeLa cells were cultured in DMEM Glutamax (Gibco) culture media supplemented with 1% penicillin/streptomycin and 10% FBS at 37 °C, 6%

CO₂ under humidity conditions. Cells were seeded in the microfluidic channels filled with culture media and cultured until confluence was reached under humidity conditions at 37 °C and 6% CO₂. Then, the real-time closed-loop control was performed in our custom-built system previously described, where a single microrobot was made to roll 6 times atop the cell monolayer on one side of the microfluidic channel. The opposite end, which had no contact with the microrobot, was used as a control, as the cells there had no influence from the microrobots but were subjected to the same stress over the experiment as the ones where the microrobot rolled. After actuation, live cells were stained green with SYBR 14, while dead cells were stained red with PI. Stock solutions were prepared according to the kit instructions (L7011, Invitrogen). To the channel, 5 μL of SYBR 14 was added and incubated for 10 min, followed by 5 μL of PI, which was incubated for another 10 min. The channels were then washed with prewarmed fresh media and observed under a fluorescence microscope. A green filter was used for SYBR 14 with an emission of 518 nm and excitation of 489 nm, and a red filter was used for PI with an emission of 636 nm and excitation of 493 nm.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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droplet microfluidics, in situ produced ultrasound/photoacoustic contrast agents, local enzymatic degradation, magnetic drug carriers, medical soft microrobot, polymersomes

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